

Ziebold's article "Precision and Sensitivity in Electron Microprobe Analysis", 50 years later.

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Summary

The statistical theory of regression and the theory of testing statistical hypotheses often use estimates of maximum likelihood in the presence of restrictions on parameters (restricted least squares estimates), as well as the likelihood ratio test as a decision criterion (the Likelihood Ratio Test).

On their basis, the work [6] proposes a solution to some problems that did not previously have a solution in quantitative X-ray spectroscopy.

The results obtained in [6] are explained here by the two-component sample analysis example.

Determination of resolution of X-ray spectral devices obtained by Ziebold for quantitative X-ray spectral electron-probe microanalysis [1] is analyzed.

It was shown that the criterion proposed by Ziebold is not the limit of detection in the case of analysis of a two-component sample. The result can be substantially improved.

The first related results were published as early as 1991, [2]

Introduction

Why so much attention to Ziebold's article? Because international and national standards are still based on this result. Laboratories in which devices have been certified by analyzing test samples are entitled to certify food products for the presence of impurities and a unified product certification system is created on this basis.

When solving nonlinear equations for a multicomponent sample, the solution obtained by Ziebold, Heinrich's empirical correction procedure [2] is used. The sample is considered in this case as quasi-binary, with the coefficients of influence of the element selected for analysis on the rest of the sample.

This article proposes a critical analysis of international standards for determining the resolution of X-ray spectral devices, methods for solving the equations of X-ray spectral analysis, and a look at the prospect of improving the analysis of a multicomponent sample.

Model

To obtain the results, we need a problem statement that is more general than in Ziebold's article.

In work [6], the problem of determining the composition of a multicomponent sample is considered as a statistical non-linear problem of estimating the vector of parameters of the signal recorded against of the noise background.

Let us have a multicomponent sample with a vector of estimated concentrations.

When the substance is irradiated with an electron beam, an X-ray beam or some other type of radiation, various chemical components enter into spectral interaction. Part of the absorbed radiation, according to quantum theory, will be re-emitted at wavelengths characteristic of certain elements that make up the sample.

The analytical signal in X-ray spectroscopy is formed as the ratio of the intensities of the characteristic radiation peaks to the similar intensity measured on the reference sample (or calculated) in order to exclude the instrumental constant.

Interaction equations can be written

$$\frac{c_i}{c_i^{st}} = \frac{I_i}{I_i^{st}} f_i(c_1, \dots, c_n) = k_i f_i(c_1, \dots, c_n) \quad (1)$$

Here, $\frac{c_i}{c_i^{st}}$ the relative concentrations (in comparison with the reference sample), $k_i = \frac{I_i}{I_i^{st}}$ the ratio of the radiation intensity of the characteristic line corrected for the background of continuous radiation to the analogous radiation from the reference sample, $f_i(c_1, \dots, c_n)$ is a complex function, rather an algorithm that describes the mechanism of interaction of elements. It is called the correction for the interaction of elements.

Then $F_i(c) = \frac{c_i}{c_i^{st} f_i(c_1, \dots, c_n)}$ is our calculated physical model. For details, I refer to the work - review

[2]. In the first approximation, the correction factors $f_i(c_1, \dots, c_n)$ are assumed to be linear functions homogeneous in concentrations.

$$f_i = \sum_j \alpha_{ij} c_j \quad (2)$$

Influence factors α_{ij} can be determined once in a calibration experiment using a set of samples with different but known element concentrations. Or they can be calculated for many cases using nonlinear equations (1). They, these coefficients, do not depend on the determined concentrations, published in the press and are used by researchers for further measurements in various laboratories without the need to re-measure them. They are, as it were, phenomenological physical constants that depend only on the physical parameters of the experiment, such as the type of exciting radiation, its energy, etc.

Formula (2) is used in quantitative optical spectroscopy, in chromatography, in X-ray fluorescence spectroscopy, in quantitative X-ray microanalysis, in x-ray diffraction analysis, analysis using synchrotron X-ray radiation. Of course not only there is used.

Ziebold in his article also proceeded from a similar model [3].

Taking into account the experimental noise and measurement errors, the general interaction equations(1) can be written.

$$\mathbf{k} = \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{c}) + \mathbf{n}, \quad (3)$$

where the all variables included in the formula are vectors. Here $\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{c})$ is a nonlinear vector physical

model, $F_i(c) = \frac{c_i}{c_i^{st} f_i(c_1, \dots, c_n)}$ as in the method of fundamental parameters, and \mathbf{c} is the vector of calculated concentrations. The vector \mathbf{k} is a random vector of experimental data that has a normal

distribution with a known dispersion matrix $\mathbf{D}_k(\mathbf{c})$. The matrix $\mathbf{D}_k(\mathbf{c})$ is diagonal, since the analytical signal errors for different components are statistically independent. Vector \mathbf{n} denotes a vector of statistical errors, a noise vector with known statistical properties.

It is assumed that interaction equations (1) take into account all elements present in the sample. That is

$$\sum_i c_i = 1, \quad (4)$$

the sum of all weight concentrations must be 100%. The analyzed samples in geology or semiconductor compositions, as well as metal alloys, are often compounds with partially known chemical formulas. Then the weight concentrations of elements are related by stoichiometric ratios. These stoichiometric relationships, together with equation (4), can be written as a matrix relationship

$$\mathbf{G}\mathbf{c} = \mathbf{u} \quad (5)$$

Where $\mathbf{G}(r \times n)$ is a non-square matrix of restriction, \mathbf{u} is a known vector. For details of definitions see [4].

One old problem

The inverse problem of X-ray spectral analysis belongs to a special class of ill-posed inverse problems. Conditions (5) in the case of such problems for the obtained solution are not satisfied automatically, the unconditional solution of the inverse problem does not belong to the domain of existence of the solution.

When solving inverse ill-posed problems in this case, solution regularization methods are used. Their essence is that with the help of additional information from a possible set of solutions, a single solution or a set of solutions are selected that do not differ from each other with a certain accuracy.

In our case, since for the direct problem the sum of the concentrations is 100%, it means that for the inverse problem for the found concentrations this should also be done. At least, this should be the case for all components participating in the spectral interaction.

Indeed, in the case of "ideal", noiseless observations, the system of physical equations plus the normalization condition (4) is an overdetermined compatible system. Moreover, if all physical equations are independent (none of the equations is a consequence of all the others), then the normalization equation should be their consequence.

If they are dependent, then an unambiguous unconditional solution does not exist, but using the normalization equation, an unambiguous solution can be obtained. It should be. But in practice this is not the case.

Taking into account the experimental noise and model errors, the system of physical equations plus the normalization condition becomes overdetermined and incompatible. The system of physical equations is not necessarily degenerate, and the unconditional solution does not necessarily add up to one. There is no algebraic solution to the problem, and the solution must be defined in some sense.

Note that the statements "inconsistent overdetermined system", "The system of physical equations is degenerate" should be used with caution, since these concepts are defined only for systems of

linear equations. It is these linear systems that arise when searching for a solution by the iterative method. Or the original system of equations can be transformed to this form.

When solving inverse ill-posed problems in this case, methods of regularization of the solution are used. Their essence is that with the help of additional information from a possible set of solutions, a single solution or a set of solutions are selected that do not differ from each other with a certain accuracy.

As far as I understand, according to the established tradition, researchers believe that an unconditional solution of physical equations exists and lies in the domain of existence of a solution and can be found by the iteration method. That the condition, the normalization equation, if it is satisfied, is only approximately, it was used only for the purpose of regularizing the solution. To find a solution, an empirical iteration procedure is used; after each iteration step the result is normalized. The answer contains both normalized and non-normalized results [2]. There is no proof of the existence of a stationary point and no criterion for stopping iterations.

As it was said, there is no algebraic solution to the problem and the solution must be defined in some sense.

At the same time, many criteria can be proposed that determine the solution for an inconsistent system of equations.

I propose to apply the criterion for maximum likelihood estimation.

In this case, the problem of finding a solution to equations (1) is formulated as a problem of statistical estimation of the signal parameters from the output of the registration system against the background of noise in the presence of a priori restrictions on these parameters. It is proposed to apply the statistical theory of parameter estimation.

In statistical regression theory, maximum likelihood estimates with restrictions on parameters are often used.

In the case of a normal noise distribution, the criterion for maximum likelihood estimation reduced to the restricted least squares estimates criterion

$$\min_{c: Gc=0} \Phi(c) = \min_{c: Gc=0} \left[\mathbf{k}^* - \mathbf{F}(\hat{\mathbf{c}}_g) \right]' \mathbf{D}_k^{-1} \left[\mathbf{k}^* - \mathbf{F}(\hat{\mathbf{c}}_g) \right] \quad (6)$$

The solution to problem (6) always exists and is unique under certain conditions; it can be obtained by the iteration method and there is a criterion for stopping the iterations. This solution coincides with the conditional solution of equation (1) if it exists. In this case, the concept of an optimal unbiased estimate of a solution or an estimate of the minimum variance is fundamental. The properties of such estimates are well studied; they are widely used in the mathematical theory of nonlinear regression when estimating the parameters of the model, [5].

For such an estimate, exist a minimum boundary for the solution variance (dispersion matrix), which is theoretically calculated as the Cramer - Rao boundary. This boundary does not depend on how the parameters are estimated. It is determined only by the amount of information contained in the processed signal (signal-to-noise ratio) [6, 7].

Next, we will restrict ourselves to considering a two-component specimen, with the help of which we will demonstrate general definitions and formulas. Normalization equation (4) is used as a condition.

$$\begin{cases} k_1 = F_1(c_1, c_2) + n_1 \\ k_2 = F_2(c_1, c_2) + n_2 \\ c_1 + c_2 = 1 \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

Ziebold's formula. Hypothesis testing and decision rules. Ziebold's definitions for microanalysis accuracy and sensitivity

Back in the last century, the international chemical consortium IUPA defined the concept and criteria for detecting a small amount of a substance in a sample. The detection criterion is based on the theory of testing statistical hypotheses and comparing the recorded signal with the threshold. The criterion states that if the recorded analytical signal x exceeds the background signal x_b by several times, then it is possible with a certain probability to assert the presence of a substance in the sample. Based on the required confidence level of the correct solution, two thresholds are selected. Depending on how much the signal exceeds the noise, a distinction is made between

- Lowest detection limit (Low Detection Limit, LDL)
- Identification limit (IDL)
- Detection with the ability to reliably determine the amount (Quantification Limit, Estimating Detection Limit, EDL)

The above definitions differ in the choice of the confidence level for three cases, respectively: when the signal reaches the first detection threshold, falls into the uncertainty interval between the first and second thresholds and exceeds the second threshold. This is a general definition. The random error is due to fluctuations in the background signal, the randomness of the analytical signal is not taken into account.

The IUPAC definition does not say anything about the method for calculating the concentrations, because, depending on the method for estimating the concentrations from the already detected analytical signal, the concentration estimate can have different accuracy (estimation variance, estimation bias). The actual quality of detection depends on this.

In order to assess the accuracy of a substance analysis method, it is necessary to calculate the theoretical solution error. The empirical method of solving equations does not allow theoretically estimating the solution error. Ziebold managed to do this in his model.

This is precisely the reason why the world scientific community has been holding on to the result of Ziebold (1967) for more than 50 years. This is the only existing result of this kind. It served as the basis for the international standard for the sensitivity of X-ray spectral microanalysis.

Ziebold, when deriving the well-known formulas that estimate the resolution and detection limit of an X-ray microanalyzer, proceeded in (7) from an overdetermined system of equations for a binary sample and a linear correction for the interaction of elements, the Ziebold-Ogilvy model [3].

Let $\delta k = k^* - k$, where k^* и k are the experimental and average (expected) values, respectively. If the comparison samples are pure elements, then system (7) will be written as an "exact" system for average values

$$\begin{cases} c_1 = k_1(c_1 + \alpha_{12}c_2) \\ c_2 = k_2(\alpha_{21}c_1 + c_2) \\ c_1 + c_2 = 1 \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

The system of equations (8) is linear in the estimated concentrations.

The system of equations (8) as an algebraic system of equations is compatible only if the system of the first two physical equations is degenerate. When noise is taken into account, this is not the case. The system of the first two physical equations in (8) is not degenerate, and its unconditional solution is equal to zero, this is a homogeneous system of equations.

Ziebold substituted experimental data instead of average values in (8), then, without any justification, considered the system of the first two physical equations to be degenerate, that is, "exact".

He took the first equation and the normalization equation and, discarding the second equation of the system as unnecessary, reduced the problem to a one-component dependence by substitution $c_2 = 1 - c_1$. He received the well-known concentration estimation formula

$$\hat{c}_1 = \frac{k_1^* \alpha_{12}}{1 - k_1^* (1 - \alpha_{12})} \quad (9)$$

The fact that he had lost exactly half of the information, the second spectral measurements, did not bother him. Using (9) as $\delta \hat{c}_1 = \varphi_1(\delta k_1)$, he calculated $(\sigma_c^2)_1 = \left(\frac{\partial \varphi_1}{\partial c}\right)^{-2} \sigma_{k_1}^2$ and obtained the result for the relative estimation error

$$\frac{\sigma_c^2}{\hat{c}_1^2} = \frac{\sigma_k^2}{k_1^2} \left[1 + \hat{c}_1 \frac{(\alpha_{12} - 1)}{\alpha_{12}} \right]^2. \quad (10)$$

And then he defined the sensitivity of the analysis as the ability to distinguish between two close estimates of concentrations

$$(\Delta c)_{\min} = \sqrt{2} \sigma_c u_{1-\alpha} \quad (11)$$

Here $u_{1-\alpha}$ is the comparison threshold, the quantile of the normal distribution, chosen from considerations of the confidence level.

Now it was possible to formulate a rule for detecting a contamination, usual rule of comparison the obtained estimate with a threshold:

the hypothesis $H_1 : c_1 > 0$ is valid, the contamination is present if $\frac{\hat{c}_1}{\sigma_{c_1}} > u_{1-\alpha}$. Otherwise

the hypothesis $H_0 : c_1 = 0$ is correct, there is no contamination .

Note that since the threshold value for the detectable contamination is equal $c_u = u_{1-\alpha} \sigma_{c_1}$, the threshold value for the analytical signal is $k_0 = F_1(c_u)$. It depends on the chosen confidence level

and the interaction equation for the given sample, compare with the IUPAC criterion. It is different for different sample compositions and different values of the confidence probability of contamination detection. From formula (10) it can be seen that the relative error nonlinearly depends on the concentration value. Then, the analytical signal detection procedure is

$$k_1^* \begin{matrix} > \\ < \end{matrix} \begin{matrix} H_1 \\ H_0 \end{matrix} k_0 \quad (12)$$

That is, Ziebold defines the detection criterion in a way that is directly opposite to the method recommended by IUPAC, he determines the level that must exceed the analytical signal according to the required probability of detecting an contamination, and not vice versa. Having chosen a confidence level of 95%, he defines the detection limit of the method as the detection of a component with this probability. If experimental data are substituted there instead of average values, then the equations will now be nonlinear in the noise of the experiment.

Cramer-Rao boundary as the minimum solution error for a two-component sample

Consider a two-component sample. Using the third equation in (8), we exclude the variable c_2 from the equations, $c_2 = 1 - c_1$.

The optimal estimate of the estimated concentration, formula (6), is reduced to the minimum of the scalar function of one variable,

$$\min_c \Phi(c) = \min_c \left\{ \left[k_1^* - F_1(c_1) \right]^2 / \sigma_{k_1}^2 + \left[k_2^* - F_2(c_1) \right]^2 / \sigma_{k_2}^2 \right\} \quad (13)$$

The estimate can be found using the iteration method. At the minimum point, the following should be performed:

$$\partial \Phi(c) / \partial c = 0 \quad (14)$$

The algorithm is described in many tutorials. We see that to obtain the optimal estimate of one variable, both registration channels and the normalization condition are used.

The potentially achievable minimum variance of the estimate is called the Cramer-Rao bound. Let us calculate the Cramer - Rao boundary variance in the described case. The scalar Cramer - Rao inequality for the lower bound of the variance of the estimate is written [6, 7, 8].

$$\sigma_c^2 \geq \sigma_{\min}^2 = \left[\frac{(\partial F_1(c_1) / \partial c_1)^2}{\sigma_{k_1}^2} + \frac{(\partial F_2(c_1) / \partial c_1)^2}{\sigma_{k_2}^2} \right]^{-1} \quad (15)$$

Considering that, (15) will be rewritten

$$\sigma_c^2 \geq \sigma_{\min}^2 = \frac{1}{(\sigma_c^{-2})_1 + (\sigma_c^{-2})_2} = (\sigma_c^2)_1 \frac{1}{1 + \frac{(\sigma_c^2)_1}{(\sigma_c^2)_2}} \quad (16)$$

where $(\sigma_c^2)_1$ and $(\sigma_c^2)_2$ are the variances of the concentration estimates obtained by discarding first one and then another equation in (7), that is, first one, then another observation channel. We see that the boundary variance for the optimal estimate is less than any of the variances obtained using only one of the spectral channels.

The formula (16) is valid for the optimal unbiased estimate obtained by solving the (14) equation for the (7) model.

Using formula (10), we get

$$\sigma_{\min}^2 = (\sigma_{k_1} \alpha_{12})^2 \frac{1}{1 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{k_1}}{\sigma_{k_2}}\right)^2 (\alpha_{21} \alpha_{12})^2} \quad (17)$$

I give in the appendix the numerical example illustrating the formula (17)¹

Correlation matrix of estimates and the confidence ellipsoid for multi-component sample. Confidence interval for two-component sample

As noted, in the case of a multicomponent sample, optimal concentration estimates are obtained using the weighted least squares method. All measured intensities are involved in obtaining each score. Therefore, all estimates will be correlated; they are characterized by a correlation matrix of estimates \mathbf{D}_c .

In the case of a single measurement of the emission spectrum of the sample, the "noise" of the analytical signal is determined by the statistics of x-ray counting. Let $\hat{\mathbf{c}}_g$ the optimal estimate, \mathbf{D}_c the correlation matrix of the concentration estimates.

Then I follow the article [12]. Let us assume the normal distribution of the deviation the obtained optimal estimates from the true values of concentrations. Then the quadratic form in the exponent of the normal distribution of estimates is described by the expression $(\hat{\mathbf{c}}_g - \mathbf{c})' \mathbf{D}_c^+ (\hat{\mathbf{c}}_g - \mathbf{c})$, it is distributed as χ^2 with ρ degrees of freedom, where $\rho = \text{rank}(\mathbf{D}_c)$, here \mathbf{D}_c^+ is the pseudoinverse matrix for the variance matrix of estimates \mathbf{D}_c . Then we get the confidence ellipsoid

$$\Pr \left\{ (\hat{\mathbf{c}}_g - \mathbf{c})' \mathbf{D}_c^+ (\hat{\mathbf{c}}_g - \mathbf{c}) \leq \chi_{1-\alpha}^2 \right\} = 1 - \alpha \quad (18)$$

where $\chi_{1-\alpha}^2$ the upper $100(1-\alpha)$ quantile of the one-sided xi-squared distribution, This means that with a confidence level $1-\alpha$, (Pr - Probability), the estimates obtained differ from the "true" concentrations by an amount lying inside this confidence ellipsoid, and all at the same time.

Our conditional minimum problem can be reformulated as a problem with additional "noiseless", accurate observations, equation(5). As a result, the matrix \mathbf{D}_c is degenerate. The matrix \mathbf{D}_c^+ is also degenerate, since the matrix \mathbf{D}_c is degenerate.

It is possible, by rotating the coordinate system in the space of concentration estimates, to pass to new statistically independent variables, matching the new variables with the direction of the axes of this confidence ellipsoid.

We will find that only for $n-r$ new variables that are linear combinations of the desired concentration estimates, the axis lengths of the confidence ellipsoid, proportional to the new variables variances, will be nonzero.

Here n is the number of equations; r is the number of conditions .

This conversion is referred to as the conversion to principal components. Let's perform this transformation.

Then $\mathbf{D}_c^+ = \mathbf{V}\Sigma\mathbf{V}'$, where \mathbf{V} is an orthogonal matrix $n \times n$, $\Sigma = \begin{bmatrix} \Sigma_{n-r} & 0 \\ 0 & 0_r \end{bmatrix}$ is a diagonal matrix

with $n-r$ non-zero components, n is the dimension of the system of equations, r is the number of constraints. Then the quadratic form in (18) is transformed

$$(\hat{\mathbf{c}}_g - \mathbf{c})'\mathbf{D}_c^+(\hat{\mathbf{c}}_g - \mathbf{c}) = (\hat{\mathbf{c}}_g - \mathbf{c})'\mathbf{V}\Sigma\mathbf{V}'(\hat{\mathbf{c}}_g - \mathbf{c}) \quad (19)$$

We introduce new variables in the concentration space $\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{V}'\mathbf{c}$. Then, for the $n-r$ components of this quadratic form, it is true $(\hat{x} - x)'\Sigma(\hat{x} - x) = \sum_{i=1}^{n-r} \sigma_{xi}^{-2} (\hat{x} - x)_i^2$, where σ_{xi}^2 are the diagonal elements of the diagonal matrix, that is, the variances of the new variables. This all is general theory.

Two-component sample

Let's see how it looks in our case of two components and normalization conditions (5). Suppose that we solved the system (7), obtained conditional optimal concentrations estimate \hat{c}_1 and \hat{c}_2 and variance of this optimal estimate σ_{\min}^2 , formula (17).

Since $c_1 + c_2 = 1$ and \hat{c}_1 and \hat{c}_2 are estimates obtained under this condition, then $\hat{c}_1 + \hat{c}_2 = 1$. Then, if $\delta c_i = \hat{c}_i - c_i$, then $\delta c_1 = -\delta c_2$, therefore $\sigma_{c1}^2 = \sigma_{c2}^2 = \sigma_{\min}^2$, and $\langle \delta c_1 \delta c_2 \rangle = -\sigma_{\min}^2$. Then, for the dispersion matrix of optimal estimates, which is equal in the limit to the Cramer - Rao boundary, we obtain

$$\mathbf{D}_{\min} = \sigma_{\min}^2 \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -1 \\ -1 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (20)$$

Where σ_{\min}^2 is the minimum achievable variance for the optimal estimate. The matrix in (20) is degenerate due to the presence of "noiseless" observation, the normalization equation.

We get further $D_{\min}^+ = \frac{1}{4\sigma_{\min}^2} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -1 \\ -1 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$, then the expression for the confidence ellipsoid, formula (19) in this case

$$\delta \mathbf{c}' \mathbf{D}_{\min}^+ \delta \mathbf{c} = \frac{1}{4\sigma_{\min}^2} \begin{bmatrix} \delta c_1 & \delta c_2 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -1 \\ -1 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \delta c_1 \\ \delta c_2 \end{bmatrix} = \frac{(\delta c_1 - \delta c_2)^2}{\sigma_{\min}^2}. \quad (21)$$

But since $c_1 + c_2 = 1$ and $\hat{c}_1 + \hat{c}_2 = 1$, then formula (21) is further transformed into a scalar equality,

$$\delta \mathbf{c}' \mathbf{D}_{\min}^+ \delta \mathbf{c} = \frac{(\hat{c}_1 - c_1)^2}{\sigma_{\min}^2} = \frac{(\hat{c}_2 - c_2)^2}{\sigma_{\min}^2}, \quad (22)$$

which is obvious in advance, since we have only one independent variable. Here \hat{c}_i and σ_{\min}^2 depend on all observations. Then

$$\begin{aligned} & \Pr \left\{ (\hat{\mathbf{c}}_g - \mathbf{c})' \mathbf{D}_c^+ (\hat{\mathbf{c}}_g - \mathbf{c}) \leq \chi_{1-\alpha}^2 \right\} = \\ & = \Pr \left\{ \frac{(\hat{c}_1 - c_1)^2}{\sigma_{\min}^2} \leq \chi_{1-\alpha}^2 \right\} = 1 - \alpha \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

Formula (23) determines the sensitivity in electron microprobe analysis for a binary sample.

Then the problem of detecting a contamination, a component of low concentration, is transformed:

Let's take the classification of confidence levels mentioned above and proposed by IUPA. We will only distinguish these probabilities not in relation to the analytical signal, but in relation to the detected contamination itself. That is, we will adopt the Ziebold strategy.

1. The optimal conditional estimate of the concentration for a two-component sample is calculated, formula (15).

2. If our assumption that there is no contamination $c_1 = 0$ is true, then on the basis of formula (23) should be $\hat{c}_1 \leq \sqrt{\chi_{1-\alpha}^2 \sigma_{\min}^2}$. Otherwise, if

$$\frac{\hat{c}_1}{\sigma_{\min}} > \sqrt{\chi_{1-\alpha}^2}, \quad (24)$$

then the contamination is detected with a confidence level $1 - \alpha$. These probabilities are selected for two detection thresholds according to the classification proposed by IUPA.

The criterion (24) for comparing the signal-to-noise ratio with the threshold is outwardly similar to the Ziebold test, but completely different values are compared with the threshold, the best optimal estimate is compared with the minimum variance. Here \hat{c}_1 and σ_{\min}^2 depend on all observations. Taking into account a priori information and information from the second channel improves the quality of detection, $\sigma_{\min}^2 < \sigma_{Ziebold}^2$.

The Ziebold's estimate bias

The above formula (16) for the boundary variance is valid for the so-called unbiased estimate, for which the mean is equal to the true value in the case of a correct hypothesis. Let us explain this. The estimation variance depends on how the content is calculated. So, if we assume that $\hat{c}_1 = k_1^*$, that is $\sigma_c^2 = \sigma_k^2$, the estimate is equal to the registered analytical signal without any correction for the

interaction, then this variance may be less than the boundary value (17). But the estimate is biased, on average $\Delta = c_1 - \bar{k}_1(c_1)$, where \bar{k} is the average for k_1^*

Now let the estimate be $\hat{c}_1 = \frac{k_1^* \alpha_{12}}{1 - k_1^* (1 - \alpha_{12})}$, formula (9). Let be $k^* = \bar{k} + \delta k$. Let us expand this

expression for estimate in a Taylor series with respect to δk . Considering the true value is

$c_1 = \frac{\bar{k}_1 \alpha_{12}}{1 - \bar{k}_1 (1 - \alpha_{12})}$, we get,

$$\frac{E(\hat{c}_1 - c_1)}{c_1} = -\frac{\sigma_k^2}{\bar{k}_1^2} c_1 \frac{(\alpha_{12} - 1)}{\alpha_{12}} \quad (25)$$

The estimate turned out to be biased, the average value of the estimate is not equal to the true value even if the hypothesis is correct. This is due to the fact that Ziebold's solution is nonlinearly dependent on experimental data. This was overlooked by Ziebold and others.

The optimal estimate discussed in the article is unbiased; it is linear in the noise of the experiment.

Conclusions

1. This article has the character of a review. It implements the strategy proposed by IUPAC for X-ray spectral analysis instruments, a powerful method of analytical chemistry. The detection limit of devices is treated by IUPAC as a statistical problem of signal detection against a background of noise. The reliability of component detection is characterized by detection quality, detection probability. Decision-making errors are possible when testing hypotheses about the presence of a signal. Some explanations are given by me in the appendix²

2. The problem of solving the equations of X-ray spectral analysis is treated as an ill-posed inverse problem.

The concept of an algebraic solution to a system of equations is replaced by the concept of statistical estimation of signal parameters against a background of noise. To detect contamination, that is, the presence of a component with a given detection probability, one must be able to calculate the theoretical solution error. In general, this can be done using maximum likelihood estimates. The presence of additional conditions - "noiseless" observations creates additional difficulties. A detailed analysis of the specifics of the problem leads to the concept of maximum likelihood estimation in the presence of restrictions on the parameters (restricted least squares estimates).

3. The use of non-square matrices, the generalized least squares method, and pseudoinverse Moore - Penrose matrices made it possible to present the problem statement in a compact and rather general form. The very description of the algorithm for obtaining the estimate, calculating the variances matrix of estimate and examples of application are contained in another article [4].

4. The solution obtained by Ziebold and his definition of the sensitivity and resolution of X-ray spectral analysis are analysed. It is shown that these definitions are insufficient and do not characterize the limiting sensitivity and resolution of X-ray spectral analysis. The lower theoretically achievable bound of the estimation variance depends, as one would expect, only on the parameters of the physical model and the signal registration errors, but not on the estimation method. This value is less than any variance of the partial estimate in (19), that is, the Ziebold boundary. The Ziebold

boundary was incorrectly interpreted as a potential minimum of the variance in the concentration estimate, as follows from the above.

5. The results obtained are valid for any correction method. The linearity of the correction factor only made it easier for us to obtain analytical results..

6. The mathematical formulation of the problem requires the specification of both a physical model of the interaction of radiation with matter and a model of noise.

The estimation accuracy limit does not depend on the method for solving the equations, but on the amount of information contained in the recorded signal, on the ratio of the input signal to noise.

7. The above results can be improved many times over in many directions. They represent only an reasoning scheme, concept. So, for example, at extremely low detectable concentrations and a reference sample of a pure element, as is customary for Ziebold, we can assume that the dispersion of the analytical signal is constant, both in the presence and absence of a signal, and is due to measurements on the reference sample, compare the IUPAC criterion. But when distinguishing the amount of a component in two compared samples, when the content of a component differs significantly from zero, one take into account the randomness of the signal Then algorithm for evaluating a random signal against the background of a random noise will look more complicated.

8. Interestingly, the description of chemical formulas using non-square matrices is successfully used in chemistry to balance chemical reactions. Using matrices, it is stated that the number of atoms on the left side of the chemical reaction should be equal to the number of atoms on the right after the reaction. Similarly, the balance of masses of these atoms or chemical compounds consisting of them is recorded. In nonequilibrium reactions, the yield of reaction products is described by the concentration vector, that is, by the same vector, the analysis of which is being discussed here. For the detailed formula derivation see [15]

Literature

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Additionally

¹ Binary sample, calculated example

Sample Mo (0.215), W (0.785) was analyzed (Goldstein JI, Newbury DE, Echlin P, Joy DC, Romig AD Jr, Lyman CE, Fiori C, Lifshin E (1992) *Scanning Electron Microscopy and X-ray Microanalysis*, 2nd ed. New York: Plenum Press) with an X-ray spectrometer in a microanalyzer under conditions $V = 20 \text{ kV}$, radiation sampling angle $\varphi = 52.5^\circ$. We assume a linear model of correction factors with coefficients $\alpha_{11} = \alpha_{22} = 1$, $\alpha_{12} = 1.641$, $\alpha_{21} = 1.078$. I have calculated the ratio of standard deviations $\sigma_{c_1^{(1)}} / \sigma_{k_1}$, $\sigma_{c_1^{(2)}} / \sigma_{k_2}$, and the theoretical minimum limit σ_{\min} / σ_k depending on the concentration c_1 and are shown in the graph. The numbers 1, 2, 3 on the graph represent, $\sigma_{c_1^{(1)}} / \sigma_{k_1}$, $\sigma_{c_1^{(2)}} / \sigma_{k_2}$ and σ_{\min} / σ_k . To calculate the Cramer - Rao boundary, we assumed that $\sigma_{k_1} = \sigma_{k_2}$. It can be seen from the graph that the Cramer - Rao boundary is always less than any of the partial boundaries when computation the content for one or another component

² Hypothesis testing and the decision rules

Let us consider the problem of detecting a low trace concentration of a substance in a multicomponent sample. For a multicomponent sample $\mathbf{c} = [c_1, \dots, c_n]^T$, two alternative hypotheses are formulated, for example against $c_i = 0$ an alternative $c_i > 0$. In the language of mathematical statistics, this is the task of testing a complex hypothesis against a complex alternative, since the real meaning of all the others $c_j > 0$, both in the first and in the second case, is unknown to us.

We can make two assumptions at any moment, state two hypotheses:

Hypothesis H_0 : no component, $c_i = 0$

hypothesis H_1 : the component is present, $c_i > 0$

The situation can be divided into four cases:

H_0 fair; choose H_0 , (probability of correct decision $1 - \alpha$)

H_0 fair; choose H_1 , (the probability of an error of the first kind α)

H_1 fair; choose H_1 , (the probability of a correct solution $1 - \beta$)

H_1 fair; choose H_0 . (the probability of an error of the second kind β)

The first and third alternatives refer to the correct solutions. The second and fourth alternatives characterized by errors.

Let in fact the component is absent, $c = 0$. At the same time, having obtained from experiment the value of the signal $k^* > k_0$ and deciding on the presence of the component, we can make a errors of the first kind α (false alarm - following the terminology of radar target detection), assuming that the component is present when it is not present, hypothesis H_1 , second line. The probability of such error is equal to α and depends on the type of conditional probability distribution $P(k | c = 0)$ and on the choice of the comparison threshold k_0 .

If it is decided that the component is absent, when it really does not exist, then the probability of a correct decision is (power of the criterion).

But if in this situation the analyzed object is still present, we can make a mistake, assuming that it does not exist, hypothesis, then, when it is, the fourth line

But if in this situation the analyzed component is still present, we can make an error, assuming that it does not exist, hypothesis H_0 , then when it is (an error of the second kind, an error of missing a signal, with probability β). The probability of this error depends on the distribution $P(k | c > 0)$ and on the actual mean of the signal $E(k^*) = F_i(c)$. If, for example $E(k^*) = k_0$, (is equal to the comparison threshold for the null hypothesis), then in 50% of cases the signal will be below the comparison threshold ($\beta = 0.5$) and the error will be large.

Our goal, of course, is to keep errors of both kinds at an acceptably low level. This cannot be done with just one comparison threshold.

We will then choose two comparison thresholds k_0 and k_1 . Let us choose the first comparison threshold $k_0 = \sigma_k t_{1-\alpha}$ in such a way that the probability of false detection of the analyzed component, when in reality this component is absent, is small,

$$\Pr\{0 \leq k^* \leq k_0\} = \int_0^{k_0} P(x | c = 0) dx = 1 - \alpha,$$

Where α is an enough small error probability.

If it is $k^* \leq k_0$ then we consider that there is no component.

Let us choose the second comparison threshold, for example, $k_1 = 2k_0$. If $k^* \geq k_1 = 2k_0$, then we consider that the component is present with a sufficiently high degree of confidence.

For such components, the signal from which also exceeded the second threshold, the probability of missing of such component β when such k^* compared with the first threshold k_0 is quite small and is numerically equal in this case to the probability of false detection α , $\alpha = \beta$. Thus, we cut off signals with insufficiently large amplitude.

The interval $k_0 = \sigma_k t_{1-\alpha} < k^* < k_1 = 2\sigma_k t_{1-\alpha}$ will be considered the interval of uncertainty. In this interval, we confidently cut off false signals with the first threshold k_0 if there are no components, but the probability of missing a signal when an object is present is too high (weak signal).

To reduce the uncertainty, if required, it is necessary to continue observations, trying to reduce σ_k , if possible, thereby bringing the first threshold closer to the second.

The graph below illustrates what has been said and is taken from a review on this topic, Limit of detection <http://www.chemometry.com/Research/LOD.html>. These definitions are accepted internationally, for example in analytical chemistry, and are agreed upon between the International Organization for Standardization (ISO) and the International Union for Pure and Applied Chemistry (IUPAC). However, the definitions are not explained in as much detail as they are here, which has led and continues to lead to misunderstandings.